

THE POTENTIAL OF THE LEADER IN MANAGING THE EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *The research of the ancient Hippocrates and Galenus defined four types of temperaments: sanguine, phlegmatic, melancholic and choleric. Unlike the ancient, Pavlov focused on the three characteristics of the central nervous system: the force or energy, the mobility (the ease with which we go from excitement to inhibition and the other way around) and the balance (the organization of the force of the two processes – excitement and inhibition). From their combination resulted four types of behavior (Băileșteanu, 2008, p. 29):*

Keywords: *assessment of the potential, ability, correlation, capacity, concept, methodology, performance, meaning, management.*

INTRODUCTION

We believe that this research is necessary, because in the literature we have studied, we have not found methods for assessing the potential of a manager in educational institutions, most management studies focus on evaluating the performance of a manager based on results.

The purpose of the study is aimed at presenting a method for evaluating the effectiveness of a manager's activities based on existing abilities, especially the ability to perform work due to potential.

Another purpose of the study is to assess the ability of the manager to work in accordance with the potential and how this correlates with the indicators of educational institutions in which managers work.

Performance management is a strategic and integrated approach aimed at ensuring long-term success in the activities of organizations by improving the performance of institutions, teams and individuals (Armstrong & Baron, 1998; Armstrong, 2001).

Effectiveness is a state of competitiveness (economic operator, manager) achieved due to the level of efficiency that ensures a stable presence over time. (Baileșteanu, 2010). Effectiveness can be determined by specific measurable results, as well as professional skills and organizational behavior.

The assessment of a leader's potential is usually defined in the literature as the process of measuring the most likely abilities that managers possess. The definition of the term "potential" varies depending on the institution. A recent study by the authors Silzer and Church (2010) revealed several meanings of the term "high potential" used in institutions. in accordance with:

- Role – potential for increasing potential for promotion to senior staff (35% of institutions studied);
- Level - potential for promotion and successful occupation of positions at two higher levels of the organizational hierarchy than the current level (25% of institutions);
- History of effectiveness - continuous report on exceptional performance (10% of institutions);
- Strategic position - key positions that are fundamental to the success of institutions (probably just a subcategory of a definition group based on "level" but aimed at well-defined positions);
- Strategic sphere - functions, organizational units, or specific geographical areas that are

central to the strategic goals of institutions at a given time.

Assessment of effectiveness is a complex process in which the dynamic participation of the components of the personality of the manager is analyzed and its reflection in the results of his work. (Burloiu, 1997).

Ability refers to a person's productivity to function taking into account not only his living environment, but also his vital abilities, moods and actions. ((Sun, 1987).

Abilities - in our opinion, this is the opportunity and ability of a person to generate valuable results, taking into account the relevant personal characteristics and external factors, and to assess the potential of a leader means to get to know each leader individually in a scientific way and objectively assess his competence.

The potential assessment is aimed at determining the maximum effectiveness of the manager. Both efficiency assessment and capacity assessment are interested in measuring efficiency. Performance estimates are usually limited to measuring actual performance and do not include performance forecasts. One of the reasons for this is that actual performance is partly determined by the requirements of the current position and thus reflects typical performance rather than maximum performance.

Evaluating the potential of a manager is important for: making managerial decisions (promotion, transfer, professional development, etc.); assisting managers in understanding how their strengths and weaknesses are perceived; determining the contribution of the manager to achieving the goals of institutions; developing decisions on remuneration for work performed.

Methods of evaluation and analysis of the manager's activities

As for the methods of evaluating effectiveness, the study showed that in the literature there are: techniques, methods, systems, etc., useful for evaluating personnel, as well as managers and management in general, and groups them by tools and methods. Among the described tools are: indicators, graphs, scales, utility function, weighted list, profilogram, matrices, tests, comparison systems. The methods are grouped into two main categories: fundamental methods [Burz and Razvan, 2010, p. 49-106]: methods based on character traits, behavior, results obtained and other methods: methods based on key criteria and methods based on status - indicators of the activities of institutions, which are the main directions for evaluating the effectiveness of management found in the literature.

The assessment of the potential to perform the work is based on self-assessment questionnaires and on assessments made by colleagues and subordinates, depending on the situation. The results are shown in the radar diagram and the XY diagram.

Methods of evaluating the activities of a manager found in the literature:

- Rampersad Model [Rampersad, 1995, p. 99];
- Virgin Direct Model (Dourado & Blakburn, 2006)
- Productivity - effectiveness - efficiency - model Bailesteanu [Bailesteanu, 2010, p. 291];
- Beilesteanu-Burza Model - Multiple Intelligence Model [Bailesteanu & Burz, 2008, p. 69-157];
- Bailesteanu-Burca model - based on the results [Bailesteanu, 2010, p. 625];
- Malcolm Baldrige Prize Model [Bailesteanu, 2010, p. 257].

The proposed method of evaluating the potential of the manager

We believe that the activities of managers should be evaluated primarily in terms of potential, and then in terms of results, because a leader without potential, even if he has results, they are not thanks to him, there are rare cases when some institutions have managers without capabilities.

Therefore, we propose in this study to evaluate the effectiveness of the manager through potential.

Obviously, it is difficult to distinguish between the potential that a manager or a leader should have. Often a manager should be a leader and a leader in his/her turn should be a manager, but at least from a theoretical point of view, we should distinguish between management and leadership. Both theory and practice discuss the relationship of leader-manager or management-leadership, but regardless of the approach, we believe that management applies primarily to objects - creates rules of stability, and leadership applies mainly to people - inspires change.

The results of the studies that have been conducted so far show the following structure of potential - measured by either total potential or partial potential. In this study, we will take the theory of potential as a whole - therefore, we will take into account the following components of potential: cognitive potential, emotional potential, social potential, practical potential and spiritual potential.

To assess the performance of the manager, we took into account as criteria and sub-criteria: personal qualities - structured into a common potential. Leaders are those who are moving in a certain direction and are able to convince others to follow them, but this will not be possible without emotional support and will always be associated with a sense of ownership and integrity change. In short, the task of leadership is what followers expect from their leaders - honesty, competence, foresight and inspiration (Kouzes & Posner, 1987). The Opportunity Perspective provides a tool for evaluating the performance of managers, determined by the potential and how it relates to the effectiveness of the institutions in which they work. Thus, we believe that a manager cannot succeed if he/she is not endowed with certain capabilities grouped into the concept of general potential.

Theoretical and methodological foundations of the study

The direction of research that we want to explore is to identify the relationship between the abilities of the head and the effectiveness of the institutions in which he works. This approach is considered as a pilot study, since so far no comprehensive empirical studies have been identified in the specialized literature aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of the work of a manager in institutions.

Conclusions

We do not deny, we really believe that economic results are those that confirm the ability of a leader, but we believe that the study of the potential of a leader is a direction that can sometimes help us find solutions to explain efficiency or inefficiency.

Overall potential, understood as a set of personality traits and developed abilities, in our opinion, is the fundamental criterion for choosing and evaluating an effective leader.

Future research directions are represented by a survey of 3 higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan, data centralization, confirmation or refutation of research hypotheses, assessment of potential and useful conclusions for these institutions.

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